

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results - Final

DELIVERABLE 8.5

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Abstract

This document presents the final version of the OPERAS-PLUS project's Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR). It outlines the maturity, uptake, and sustainability of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and provides a consolidated account of dissemination and exploitation activities implemented throughout the project. The report reflects the current status of the KERs, summarises pathways for their continued use beyond the project's duration, and highlights OPERAS' progress toward becoming a sustainable European Research Infrastructure.

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Executive summary

OPERAS is the European Research Infrastructure dedicated to advancing open scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). As a distributed infrastructure, OPERAS was formally established as an international non-profit association (AISBL) in early 2020 and included on the ESFRI roadmap in 2021. The OPERAS-PLUS project has played a key role in supporting its transition toward ERIC status, planned for 2028, by strengthening its governance, services, visibility, and long-term sustainability.

This Final Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) outlines how the project has contributed to the uptake, reuse, and sustainability of its main outcomes. At the core of the exploitation strategy are five Key Exploitable Results (KERs), developed to address the critical components of OPERAS' operational and strategic model.

The first Key Exploitable Result "OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework" establishes the core frameworks required for OPERAS to evolve into a fully operational European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). This includes the formation of the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR), development of a multiannual financial plan, and preparation of key legal and strategic documents - such as governance models and funding mechanisms. Complementary elements include a pan-European employment policy framework, the development of a risk management strategy, and alignment with ISO-based standards for quality and service management. Together, these outputs form the institutional and procedural backbone for OPERAS' transition to a sustainable and recognised European research infrastructure.

The second Key Exploitable Result "OPERAS Innovation Lab" establishes the OPERAS Innovation Lab as a strategic mechanism for fostering innovation in scholarly communication in SSH. Emerging from research and coordination activities in WP4, the Lab is structured around two core functions - observatory and accelerator - and aims to provide OPERAS with dedicated capacity to surface emerging needs, evaluate novel outputs, and support pilot development. During the project, it launched a case study programme, published evaluation guidelines, and began prototyping support instruments and pilot coordination mechanisms. The Lab has already been mobilised to support innovation-related tasks in new projects such as GRAPHIA and LUMEN, demonstrating its role as an interface between OPERAS and externally funded initiatives. As a transitional structure, the Lab connects project-based experimentation with future infrastructure-level operations and is now being developed further with the goal of integration into the OPERAS ERIC model.

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The third Key Exploitable Result “OPERAS portfolio of services” focuses on structuring and developing the OPERAS portfolio of services as a core component of the infrastructure. It supports the transition from project-based developments to an operational service offer, including the formalisation of service types, integration into catalogues, adoption of lightweight service management practices (FitSM) and enhanced alignment with stakeholder needs across the SSH domain. During the project, core services moved from development into production, providing a foundation for future integration and reuse across collaborative initiatives. The focus is now on consolidating this offer and establishing sustainable operational models to support long-term service delivery within OPERAS.

The fourth Key Exploitable Result “OPERAS user training framework” aims to establish a comprehensive, modular training framework tailored to the needs of OPERAS service users and providers. Developed under WP6, it includes the collection and organisation of training activities and materials across OPERAS services, integration of internal and external programmes (such as FitSM, Skills4EOSC), and alignment with FAIR and core Open Science values. In parallel, a complementary methodological component - UCQ-FRAME - has also been developed within WP6 to support the evaluation of user engagement and user experience across OPERAS services. UCQ-FRAME aligns with the broader objectives of the work package by embedding human-centred design principles into service development practices.

The fifth Key Exploitable Result “OPERAS national nodes” defines the role of National Nodes as decentralised structures that support OPERAS’ mission at the country level. Developed under WP7, this result provides a flexible framework for National Nodes, outlining their contribution to community engagement, local coordination, training, and multilingual scholarly communication. A common roadmap was prepared and adopted across existing and emerging nodes, supported by guidelines on sustainability, shared metrics, and national integration strategies. OPERAS currently counts 13 national nodes, with varying levels of formalisation. While legal and operational alignment with the central hub is still in progress, including the drafting of a Memorandum of Understanding, the Nodes have collectively articulated a shared vision and are progressively being integrated into OPERAS’ distributed governance model, with a view toward their formal inclusion in the future ERIC structure.

These results have been developed in close coordination with the broader OPERAS strategy and are supported by sustainability planning across organisational, technical, and financial dimensions. Each KER has been tracked and refined throughout the project, with dedicated champions ensuring continuity, relevance, and alignment with stakeholder needs.

Dissemination in OPERAS-PLUS is a core element of infrastructure-building, closely tied to OPERAS' distributed structure and community-led approach. Dissemination was aligned with the implementation of project results and structured around the operational logic of each KER, while remaining embedded in OPERAS' broader infrastructure-building efforts. It involves multiple governance and community integration mechanisms, such as the Executive Assembly, General Assembly, National Nodes, the Assembly of Commons, the Scientific Advisory Board, and Special Interest Groups. While WP8 led communication and dissemination efforts at the project level, other work packages - such as WP6 or WP4 via the Innovation Lab - also contributed directly to community-facing communication. Activities included multilingual publications, policy briefs, events, blogs, and targeted outreach. More importantly, dissemination was driven by OPERAS members themselves, who acted as communicators, interpreters, and facilitators within their own local and disciplinary networks. This community-based model fostered trust, participation, and alignment between OPERAS' strategic vision and the diverse realities of the SSH landscape.

This final PEDR reflects a shift from project-based communication toward embedded, infrastructure-level dissemination and exploitation. It demonstrates that the foundation laid by OPERAS-PLUS - through its stakeholder networks, governance mechanisms, and services - supports the long-term viability and strategic positioning of OPERAS within the evolving European research landscape. These achievements form the basis for future implementation. As OPERAS transitions into an ERIC, the measures outlined in this report will continue to evolve through operational roll-out, stakeholder alignment, and integration into long-term strategic roadmaps.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the final update of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) for the OPERAS-PLUS project. It builds upon Deliverables [D8.3 \(initial PEDR\)](#) and [D8.4 \(interim update\)](#) by summarising the outcomes achieved, sustainability mechanisms in place, and strategic directions established for continued impact. The purpose of this final version is to provide a consolidated view of how dissemination and exploitation activities have contributed to the uptake, visibility, and long-term viability of the project's key results. Duplication with D8.4 has been deliberately avoided by streamlining core progress narratives and relocating technical details to the annex.

Methodological approach

The overall methodology has remained consistent throughout the project and includes documentation analysis, ongoing tracking of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), performance indicators, and regular internal consultation with work package leaders and representatives of the broader OPERAS community. A core part of this approach has been the identification of five KERs, each coordinated by a dedicated KER champion, with status and actions documented via the OPERAS-PLUS Confluence platform. This final update consolidates the results of that process and presents the full set of dissemination and exploitation activities completed over the course of the project.

Strategic use of the plan

Throughout the OPERAS-PLUS lifecycle, the PEDR served not only as a compliance requirement but as an integral strategic tool. It supported OPERAS in reinforcing its identity as a visible, credible, and coordinated research infrastructure. Efforts around exploitation focused on the adoption and reuse of services and frameworks, connection to national ecosystems, and integration into existing infrastructures. OPERAS ensured alignment with European initiatives, and built forward-looking relationships with institutional, policy, and community stakeholders. Dissemination activities were coordinated across the consortium to support multilingualism, inclusivity, and relevance to SSH. Channels included the OPERAS website, newsletter, blog, social media, policy briefs, webinars, and presence at key events. These actions contributed to strengthening OPERAS' profile and positioning within the broader Open Science ecosystem. The PEDR process laid a foundation for OPERAS to continue operating as a sustainable research infrastructure beyond the lifetime of OPERAS-PLUS. As the project closes, OPERAS carries forward a functional portfolio of services, structured

engagement mechanisms, and increased readiness for ERIC status. As OPERAS enters the next phase of its institutional development, the PEDR will continue to guide the practical implementation of key results. Its role will shift from strategic alignment to operational execution, serving as a living framework for consolidating outcomes and tracking their evolution post-project.

Structure of the report

The structure of this report reflects the logic of the PEDR process. Following this introduction:

- Section 2 provides a consolidated view of the five Key Exploitable Results (KERs), with dedicated entries outlining their description, progress, and sustainability prospects.
- Section 3 presents an overview of how dissemination and exploitation were implemented in practice across the project.
- Section 4 concludes with key reflections and next steps.
- All supporting tables, including both Horizon Results Platform templates and internal project summaries, are provided in the Annex.

2. Summary view on Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

This section presents a consolidated view of the five Key Exploitable Results (KERs) developed within OPERAS-PLUS. Each KER represents a strategic element of the OPERAS infrastructure, contributing to its operational capacity, community engagement, and long-term sustainability. For clarity and focus, each KER is provided with a concise definition, a summary of progress and results achieved during the project, and an outlook on future use and sustainability. To avoid duplication and improve readability, detailed data tables - including those aligned with the Horizon Results Platform format and other relevant indicators - were moved to the Annex, while the main text focuses on the narrative and strategic status of each result. In addition to documenting progress, this section highlights how each result is positioned for future uptake. Where relevant, links to planned actions and integration pathways are made explicit to support the transition from project output to long-term assets.

KER1: OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework

Description

The OPERAS core governance, finance, and management Framework (KER1) encompasses the foundational elements necessary for transitioning OPERAS into a

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European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).

This KER consolidates several originally separate results defined in the grant agreement into a single, integrated framework to support the preparation for a coherent and efficient ERIC transition and long-term operational stability. It includes the development and implementation of various models and policies such as governance, financial sustainability, human resources, risk management and capacity planning. Specifically, KER1 covers the creation of the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR), the drafting of ERIC statutes and Technical & Scientific Description (TSD) of OPERAS Research Infrastructure, the preparation of a multiannual financial plan, and the development of a pan-European employment framework natively supporting equal opportunity and assessing RESAVER pan-European pension fund. It also includes a comprehensive risk management strategy and capacity plan based on ISO standards, supporting the overall compliance and maturity of OPERAS as it enters the ERIC application process. The aim is to ensure that OPERAS strengthens as a robust and sustainable research infrastructure, facilitating open scholarly communication within the SSH.

Progress

Over the course of the OPERAS-PLUS project, KER1 moved from strategic planning to development across governance, legal, and operational areas. The Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) was formally established in November 2023. With representatives from 12 countries, it becomes the central body for decision-making around the ERIC transition. Since its first meeting on January 9th, 2024, it meets every 3 or 4 months, has adopted its Terms of Reference, reviewed and amended the draft ERIC statutes, and coordinated preparatory steps for national commitments. The draft statutes and several related documents remain under active discussion and are expected to be finalised by the end of the project (D3.3). A multiannual financial framework was developed and presented to the BGR, including projections through 2032, cost scenarios, a host premium model, and a draft in-kind contributions policy.

OPERAS is developing its risk management framework and capacity plan, based on ISO 9001 and ISO/IEC 31000 standards, as part of the OPERAS Integrated Management System. In parallel, a pan-European employment framework was prepared, with a harmonised salary scale and country correction coefficients introduced in January 2024.

These components are being consolidated for the step 1 of the ERIC application, which is currently under development, with submission foreseen by the end of 2025.

In parallel, dissemination and engagement actions linked to KER1 were carried out

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through OPERAS' internal governance bodies. The Executive Assembly, the General Assembly, the Assembly of Commons, the Scientific Advisory Committee, and Strategy and Technical Board were actively involved in reviewing drafts and contributing to the development process, with 80% of planned internal interactions completed during the first reporting period. As of March 2025, 12 countries were represented in the BGR meeting, and 13 countries had formal national representation (National Nodes) within the OPERAS structure. This reflects continued progress in securing national-level commitment to the OPERAS ERIC process.

Sustainability

KER1 provides the operational and institutional frameworks that will carry OPERAS beyond the lifetime of OPERAS-PLUS. Its key components - including the ERIC statutes, multiannual financial model, risk management plan, and employment framework - are being consolidated into the ERIC application dossier currently under preparation. These elements are designed for direct reuse and will serve as the legal and organisational foundation for the future OPERAS ERIC. Coordination is maintained through the BGR, which continues to meet and oversee final adjustments, ministerial engagement, and the submission of the ERIC application Step 1 foreseen by the end of 2025. Until the formal establishment of the ERIC, coordination and maintenance of KER1 outputs will be ensured through OPERAS AISBL and the BGR. Risk and capacity planning are integrated into OPERAS' internal management system, and the HR and financial models developed under OPERAS AISBL are ready for transfer into the ERIC structure.

KER1 is closely linked to other areas of the project - including innovation, services, training, and national engagement - ensuring coherence across institutional and operational development.

Furthermore, the frameworks produced through KER1 are aligned with broader ERIC standards and practices, and are expected to serve as useful references for other emerging infrastructures, particularly within the SSH domain.

KER2: OPERAS Innovation Lab

Description

The [OPERAS Innovation Lab](#) is a support and coordination mechanism established to foster innovation in scholarly communication in the SSH.

Originally proposed as a response to the findings of the OPERAS-P project, the Lab was developed in OPERAS-PLUS under WP4 to serve as a knowledge hub and catalyst for experimentation, supporting researchers, service providers, and infrastructure actors.

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Its goal is to assist stakeholders in developing, testing, and scaling new models, tools, and practices in open scholarly communication.

This two-part structure – observatory and accelerator – was adopted following an internal revision of the Lab’s initial model during the course of the project. The Lab operates through the observatory, which monitors emerging practices and produces knowledge outputs, and the accelerator, which provides targeted support for pilot services, partnerships, and experimentation. Tools such as the Bank of Ideas and the Pilot portfolio are in early development and serve to organise internal knowledge and prepare for future structured support.

The Lab is closely connected to OPERAS community bodies including Special Interest Groups, National Nodes, and the Assembly of Commons, and maintains engagement with external partners across academia, civil society, and the private sector. It is intended to become a long-term element of OPERAS ERIC, embedding innovation as a sustained, participatory process within the infrastructure’s future operations.

Progress

Over the course of OPERAS-PLUS, the Innovation Lab has transitioned from a conceptual framework into a functional coordination space embedded in the OPERAS infrastructure. This transition included a shift from a project-defined task structure to a regular, ongoing effort carried out by a dedicated team operating beyond the formal boundaries of WP4.

The Lab’s observatory activities produced a multi-part case study on SSH innovation practices, informed by desk research, group interviews, and a community validation workshop at the OPERAS Conference 2024 in Zadar. The resulting guidelines and analysis were published on the Lab’s website, alongside contributions from external authors. A dedicated evaluation framework for innovative outputs was developed to support OPERAS services and projects.

On the accelerator side, the Lab started to design the structure of a project support programme, considered its first pilot project (the JATS XML Converter in partnership with SRCE), and began preparing a broader portfolio of candidate services, including pilots connected to new projects such as GRAPHIA and LUMEN. Internal tools such as the Bank of Ideas and pilot templates are under iterative development and being tested within OPERAS structures.

The Lab has consistently communicated its work through a dedicated website, blog posts, and OPERAS-wide channels (social media, newsletter, etc.). It published the case study series, methodological guidelines, and guest contributions throughout 2023-25.

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Engagement with internal structures such as Special Interest Groups, the Assembly of Commons, and other WPs has been continuous, including presentations at key community events (i.e. Munin 2023, ADHO DH 2023, OPERAS Conf' 2024, RESSH 2024). In early 2025, the Lab extended its outreach by organising an [innovation workshop in Luxembourg](#) with EU innovation stakeholders, aimed at exploring governance models, funding strategies, and cross-sector collaboration in the SSH innovation landscape.

Sustainability

The Innovation Lab is positioned to become a long-term strategic function within the OPERAS infrastructure. Further work is underway to expand the scope of the Lab through the development of an innovation management framework and community-based workflows. As OPERAS transitions into an ERIC, the Innovation Lab is envisioned as a service-oriented structure, offering project-level and cross-project innovation support, analytical insight, and coordination capacity for emerging SSH research needs.

KER3: OPERAS portfolio of services

Description

OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. It aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. It offers a range of services that greatly benefit researchers and authors in the SSH community. These services enable researchers to discover open scholarly resources, improve the quality of peer-review practices, engage in collaborative citizen science projects, and more.

There are three types of services provided by OPERAS:

1. **Managed:** Services managed by OPERAS, responsible for overall coordination, delivery and evolution.
2. **Community:** Services managed directly by community providers but discoverable through the OPERAS ERIC catalogue. These services are required to have sustainable structures to be established, but receive direct OPERAS participation, contribution and support.
3. **Internal:** Services necessary for managing and operating the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, both technical and non-technical.

These services are grouped into eight categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, and Operational and

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Collaboration Tools.

OPERAS Service Catalogue

Discovery Services

Exploring Social Sciences and Humanities research in multiple languages

Analytics Services

Measuring usage and impact of Open Access content

Research for Society Services

Activating participatory research in Citizen Science

Quality Assurance Services

Increasing transparency about peer review for monographs

Finding editorial services for academic publishing

Fostering research dialogues and impact through academic blogging

The current service catalogue is provided below:

Managed Services

1. GoTriple: Facilitates the discovery of almost 20 million multilingual scholarly content from a single access point (publications, authors, projects).
2. Pathfinder: Enhances the visibility of editorial services and guides editors, editorial managers and authors to discover the best service to fit their needs.
3. Metrics: Collects usage and impact metrics from various sources related to published Open Access books, which can be accessed, displayed and analysed from a centralised database.
4. VERA: Allows SSH researchers to build citizen science projects together with diverse stakeholders and provides tools to facilitate collaboration and project development.

Community Services

5. Hypotheses: Provides a space for SSH research blogs, fostering innovative formats of scholarly communication and offering multilingual content.
6. PRISM: Aims to improve transparency and trust in Open Access book publishing by providing standardised information about the peer-review process.

There are other services in various stages of development that may be included in the OPERAS service catalogue in future. One example is Mondaecus, a platform offering a collaborative environment for researchers and professionals to translate and edit

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scientific documents in multiple languages, which received support from the OPERAS-PLUS project for an initial design study and prototype. Similarly, the OPERAS Innovation Lab is planned to be added to the Service Catalogue in 2025.

OPERAS Internal Services

OPERAS ID

Messaging

Internal services include:

1. [FitSM®](#): a training and certification program in lightweight service management mainly for OPERAS ERIC members.
2. [OPERAS ID](#): provides a single solution for user registration across all services, offering federated identity authentication such as ORCID, Google, EGI Check-in.
3. [Messaging](#): dedicated self-managed Mattermost server for collaborative messaging.

In addition, OPERAS offers a range of services for the OPERAS internal community such as consultancy on FAIR data management and Open Science, IT service management (ITSM), policy development, and coordination in the following areas:

- Strategy and Policy
- Legal and Finance
- Community Management
- Communication and Outreach
- Service Management and Technology
- National Nodes Structuralisation
- Project Management and Planning

As a legal entity, OPERAS ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its services while aiming to improve the quality and efficiency of scholarly communication in SSH.

Progress

The OPERAS service roadmap tracks the current status of the various services, as well as the timing of key milestones, mainly for planned service phase changes. This view helps to link to the communications teams for preparing relevant messages. It also maps to the projects and funding sources that are supporting the development. This strategic overview is crucial as many of the OPERAS services are spread across almost all service

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phases with varying timings as well.

Service	Status	Type	Category	2022				2023				2024				2025				Funding Source
				Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4													
GoTriple	Production	Managed	Discovery	[Light Green]				TRIPLE												
Metrics	Production	Managed	Analytics	[Light Green]				OPERAS-PLUS												
VERA	Production	Managed	Research4Society	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Light Green]	COESO											
Pathfinder	Beta	Managed	Discovery	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Light Green]	OPERAS-PLUS											
Fiscal Hosting	Beta	Managed	Professional	[Grey]	[Grey]	[Grey]	[Grey]	[Light Green]	OPERAS AISBL											
Innovation Lab	Beta	Managed	Collaboration	[Grey]	[Orange]	[Light Green]	OPERAS-PLUS													
Hypotheses	Production	Community	Research4Society	[Light Green]	OpenEdition															
PRISM	Production	Community	Quality Assurance	[Light Green]	OPERAS-PLUS															
Mondaecus	Alpha	Community	Multilingualism	[Orange]	OPERAS-PLUS															
FitSM Training	Production	Internal	Training	[Grey]	[Red]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Light Green]	OPERAS, Projects, Fees											
Messaging (Mattermost)	Production	Internal	Collaboration	[Grey]	[Grey]	[Grey]	[Red]	[Light Green]	COESO, OPERAS-PLUS											
OPERAS ID (AAI)	Production	Internal	Operations	[Grey]	[Orange]	[Orange]	[Light Green]	OPERAS AISBL												

Figure 1: OPERAS Service Roadmap Overview

At the start of 2022, there were only 4 services in Beta, with 6 services either in the design phase or earlier. By mid-2023, 5 services were in production, 4 in Beta, 1 in Alpha and only 1 still under design. By Q1 2025, 8 services were in production, 2 in Beta and 1 in Alpha. The following table provides an overview of the service phase changes for each service.

Service	Q1 2022	Q3 2023	Q1 2025
GoTriple	Beta	Production	Production
Metrics	Beta	Beta	Production
VERA	Design	Beta	Production
Pathfinder	Design	Beta	Beta
Hypotheses	Production	Production	Production
Fiscal Hosting	N/A	Alpha	Beta
PRISM	Beta	Production	Production
Mondaecus	Design	Design	Alpha

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Service	Q1 2022	Q3 2023	Q1 2025
FitSM Training	N/A	Production	Production
Messaging	N/A	Production	Production
OPERAS ID	N/A	Beta	Production

Table 1: Service Phase Changes

Service dissemination

Dissemination activities related to the OPERAS services were a critical component of the OPERAS-PLUS project, aimed at ensuring the visibility, integration, and sustainable uptake of the service portfolio within the broader Open Science landscape.

Throughout the project, dissemination efforts consistently combined two levels of action: promoting the [OPERAS Service Catalogue](#) as a coherent and strategic offer, and supporting the dissemination of individual services as they became operational. More recently, the Service Catalogue was presented at events including the [OPERAS Conference 2024](#), the [E-RIHS Public Event](#), and [CONFOA 2024](#), which helped to anchor the portfolio within the European research community. Dissemination activities also benefited from the inclusion of OPERAS services in the [SSH Open Marketplace](#) as well as description updates of existing services, collaboration with the [EURISE network](#), and alignment with EOSC initiatives, further reinforcing their visibility and integration.

In parallel, specific dissemination actions targeted individual services. GoTriple, the discovery platform, was promoted at the [TrustOn 2024 workshop](#), emphasising its role in multilingual access to open scholarly content in SSH. In addition, events focused on the service improvement, such as the [First Researcher Forum](#) and [First Mutual Learning Exercise](#) organised within the [ATRIUM project](#), also helped raise awareness about the GoTriple service within end users and data providers. VERA was presented at international events such as the [LIBER Conference](#), TrustOn 2024 and the [Digital Governance Series at the UN Science Summit](#), positioning it within the evolving citizen science and participatory research landscape. Pathfinder underwent a relaunch with an improved onboarding process and renewed outreach efforts, notably through the OPERAS Assembly of Commons and Scientific Advisory Committee, integrating additional services into the catalogue and strengthening the provider network.

OPERAS Metrics advanced its dissemination through a [dedicated training webinar](#) held by the [GraspOS project](#) and expanded its outreach by displaying usage indicators

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within [UPLOpen](#). PRISM service, which improves the transparency on the peer-review processes of OA books, was also showcased in [a dedicated GraspOS webinar](#).

Dissemination activities extended beyond events and webinars. OPERAS systematically incorporated service information into its communication materials, including website updates, newsletters, social media, training modules, and onboarding resources. National Nodes contributed increasingly to dissemination at the national level, helping to localise OPERAS services within local research environments and direct community engagement.

Service usage and KPIs

Service usage and key performance indicators (KPIs) are crucial components in evaluating the effectiveness and impact of a service. Service usage pertains to the extent to which a service is utilised by its intended audience, encompassing metrics such as the number of users, frequency of usage and the specific features accessed. Monitoring service usage can provide insights into user engagement and the service's overall value to the target audience.

OPERAS deploys a mix of collection mechanisms comprising tools such as Matomo/Mixpanel as well as manual collection on a monthly basis (reviewed during each Services and Technology Board - STB) extracting key information from local databases. During each STB, KPIs are reviewed and additional intelligence is extracted such as usage behavior. Below are a few examples of KPIs.

It's important to note that the majority of services moved into production at the end of 2023, therefore historical data, trends and overall numbers are in their infancy.

- As of May 2025, GoTriple contains almost 20 million documents, reaching an average of 25,000 monthly visits with a max month of 44,000 and has almost 600 registered users. We can already see that users with registered accounts spend twice as much time on site and increased traffic coming from having been indexed in AI platforms.
- OPERAS Metrics tracked over 10,000 unique book views monthly with 82 publishers onboarded and over 300 publishers with at least one metric. Usage increases have started to take off and will continue thanks to the integration with UPLopen.
- Pathfinder lists 42 services from 9 providers and has started to generate interest for onboarding new OPERAS members.
- VERA counted almost 300 user profiles and 120 projects. Efforts need to be made to encourage users to make profiles public versus the default setting of private to make activities taking place more visible.

- Hypotheses maintains ~5,000 active blogs with ~20,000 user accounts and regularly sees over 1 million visits per month and remains the most mature and used services, which has been in service since 2009.
- Over 300 FitSM certifications have been facilitated through more than 20 courses by the OPERAS AISBL, its affiliates, and associated trainer network. OPERAS is an official FitSM Training Organisation accredited by APMG.

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Sustainability

The OPERAS service portfolio is transitioning from project-based development towards a model of permanent operational management, anchored by the adoption of FitSM practices for lightweight service management and quality assurance. In the immediate term, sustainability is supported by a combination of project funding and in-kind contributions from OPERAS members and partners. As OPERAS moves towards the establishment of an ERIC, national contributions are foreseen as a future mechanism to strengthen the long-term operational base.

In parallel, OPERAS is exploring additional sustainability pathways, including service specific strategies aligned with the principles of public mission support. Potential approaches under consideration include value-added services, freemium models, white-label adaptations, and enhanced project-based collaborations, always respecting the fundamental commitment to open scholarly communication and public good provision. New projects such as GRAPHIA, LUMEN, and FASCA are already contributing practical use cases, technical enhancements, and additional resources to reinforce the service ecosystem, with further opportunities being pursued through upcoming funding calls.

OPERAS is pursuing a diversified strategy that combines public funding, collaborative

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project frameworks, institutional engagement (financial and in-kind support), and operational efficiencies to ensure resilience, adaptability, and service continuity across its distributed infrastructure.

KER4: OPERAS user training framework

Description

The OPERAS User Training Framework provides a systematic approach to user training, skills development and capacity building, tailored to the needs of the SSH community and the wider scholarly communication ecosystem. It is being developed under Task 6.4 of OPERAS-PLUS (M20-M36), with the final deliverable planned as D6.3 "Framework for the development of training in open science and scholarly communication" in M36 (August 2025).

While the framework is being finalised within OPERAS-PLUS, OPERAS-related training activities have been primarily delivered through a diverse ecosystem of projects and initiatives, including [TRIPLE](#), [COESO](#), [DIAMAS](#), [CRAFT-OA](#), [The European Diamond Capacity Hub \(EDCH\)](#) and [Skills4EOSC](#). The framework acts as a coordination mechanism, building on these existing resources and community capacities rather than duplicating efforts.

It aims to support OPERAS' transition to an ERIC by providing a structured approach to integrating training as a cross-cutting activity within the OPERAS operational model, thereby strengthening service uptake, user engagement and community building.

In parallel, a complementary methodological component - UCQ-FRAME - has also been developed within WP6 to support the evaluation of user engagement and user experience across OPERAS services. UCQ-FRAME aligns with the broader objectives of the work package by embedding human-centred design principles into service development practices. The framework has been tested on key services such as GoTriple using a multi-method evaluation approach (heuristic evaluation, moderated and unmoderated usability testing) and refined based on user feedback. Its relevance to SSH-specific UX and usability assessment has been confirmed, and its core structure is now being developed into the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design, an evolving resource to support teams across OPERAS in applying user-centred practices. As FitSM provides a structured basis for service management, the UCQ-FRAME will be further used to support human-centred service development within the OPERAS infrastructure and in new projects.

Scope and focus

The framework covers several focus areas, reflecting both the thematic priorities of OPERAS services and the wider training needs of the SSH:

- Scholarly communication and publishing, with an emphasis on Diamond Open Access models and community-led publishing, building on initiatives such as DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA and EDCH.
- Open science and Research Data Management (RDM), using FAIR-by-design approaches and SSH-tailored minimum viable skill sets, building on FAIRsFAIR, SSHOC and Skills4EOSC.
- Technical capacity building on EOSC architecture, onboarding, metadata quality and OPERAS services such as GoTriple.
- Participatory and interdisciplinary research skills, supported by COESO (citizen science) and ATRIUM (impact maximisation workshops).
- Stakeholder engagement, addressing the needs of citizen scientists, policy makers, funders and infrastructure providers.
- Internal service-related training, including FitSM, FAIR-by-design, user support workflows and service quality assurance processes, supporting OPERAS service management practices towards ERIC readiness.

Methodology and approach

The framework approach includes

- Leveraging existing outputs from cross-cutting projects to ensure complementarity and avoid duplication.
- Developing FAIR-by-design training materials, following guidelines from activities and initiatives such as the [TRIPLE Training Toolkit](#) and the [Skills4EOSC Competence Centre](#).
- Supporting the integration of training as a cross-cutting, service-enabling function within OPERAS, aligned with FitSM principles, with proposed quality management, KPIs, and user engagement workflows to inform future adoption into OPERAS' service management system.
- Supporting decentralised delivery models through national nodes and community networks, taking into account local and disciplinary needs.
- Integration with OPERAS stakeholder engagement strategies, positioning training as an enabler for community building and service uptake ([D6.1](#), [D6.2](#), [MS10](#)).

Alignment with OPERAS strategic priorities

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The framework contributes to OPERAS priorities by:

- Increasing user engagement and capacity to use OPERAS services.
- Supporting the adoption of community-led scholarly communication and open science services.
- Promoting a culture of open science and FAIR practices in SSH.
- Enable interoperability with EOSC.
- Promote multilingualism, diversity and equity in training.
- Strengthen OPERAS internal service management by embedding training as a sustainable activity.

Progress

While the formalisation of the framework continues under Task 6.4, OPERAS-related training continues to be developed and delivered through OPERAS-related projects. These activities support capacity building and user engagement across SSH communities.

Key contributions include

- Development of open and reusable SSH-specific training resources and toolkits (e.g. [TRIPLE](#), [GoTriple Pundit Annotation Tools](#), [Trust Building Systems \(TBS\)](#), [multilingual vocabulary training](#), EOSC integration, [FAIR-by-design](#) workshops).
- Training materials on publishers' metadata quality delivered at two summer schools for journal editors within the CRAFT-OA project.
- Promoting participatory skills and interdisciplinary engagement through [COESO](#) and [ATRIUM](#).
- Implementation of webinars, workshops and outreach events involving different stakeholders (e.g. [in-person workshops and conferences](#), [online webinars](#), [virtual workshops](#), specific formats with strong stakeholder involvement like [ThatCamp](#), [practical implementation and technical training](#), [funding](#) and [crowdfunding](#) opportunities, [cross-project collaboration](#), [multilingual aspects](#), etc.).
- Preparation of learning pathways and pilot courses for key communities drawing on [EDCH's Training Platform](#) (available in June 2025) and [Skills4EOSC](#) (available in June 2025).
- Organisation of FitSM service management training with 57 certified participants (provided directly by OPERAS AISBL), strengthening internal service capabilities (e.g. in [FitSM training in Zadar](#)).

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Within Task 6.4, specific progress includes

- Drafting the OPERAS [training strategy](#), identifying key user groups, providers and priorities ([video](#)).
- Conceptualise the framework as a modular, decision-support toolkit to assist service teams in training design.
- Creation of structured templates for training design, including needs assessment, learner analysis, method selection and alignment grids.
- Pilot activities and webinars, including internal [UX evaluation training](#) and EOSC alignment sessions.

The testing and validation phase is planned for June 2025 (M34), involving selected services and providers, using existing user feedback mechanisms.

Despite the distributed nature of the training activities, this diversity provides a rich base of models and communities of practice to inform the development of the framework as a modular, community-driven and multimodal structure, aligned with OPERAS governance and intended for integration into the OPERAS Integrated Management System (IMS)¹.

Sustainability

The framework will be developed with sustainability as a guiding principle, focusing on re-use, community ownership and alignment with OPERAS capacities and the European Open Science skills landscape.

The framework is designed to support its potential integration into the OPERAS service portfolio as a cross-cutting enabler, facilitating user engagement and capacity building. While formal adoption within OPERAS governance is a future step, the current design is aligned with FitSM principles and compatible with OPERAS service management practices.

Sustainability mechanisms include:

- Alignment with OPERAS IMS, SMS and quality management processes.
- Leveraging community capacity and existing training resources from TRIPLE, COESO, DIAMAS, EDCH and others.
- Promote decentralised, community-led delivery models through national nodes, SIGs and service teams.
- Supporting autonomous training design through a modular toolkit piloted during OPERAS-PLUS.

¹ The OPERAS IMS includes also its Service Management System (SMS)

Finally, the framework aims to align with broader European initiatives on open science skills (e.g. Skills4EOSC Competence Centres).

KER5: OPERAS national nodes

Description

OPERAS national nodes are at different stages of development in several countries; their roles include communication, dissemination, coordination, and policy interfacing. Altogether, 13 national nodes are operating within OPERAS, including the following country representatives: Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, United Kingdom.

Progress

During OPERAS-PLUS, a total of 14 ordinary members joined the OPERAS infrastructure: France 4, Spain 1, Denmark 1, Cyprus 1, UK 3, Poland 2, Germany 1 and Croatia 1 as well as 3 core members and 1 supporting member. Altogether, 4 of the nodes had soft and/or official launches during the project (5 already started their work before OPERAS-PLUS began). At the end of May 2024, OPERAS-SI, the Slovenian National Node, had their kick-off meeting. October 2024 was significant for OPERAS-ES (Spain) when it had its official national event. The year 2024 was important for France as well, as it also launched OPERAS-FR in the beginning of the year. The beginning of 2025 was marked by the official launch of OPERAS-UK.

A consortium of OPERAS five national nodes acted together and applied for the Erasmus+ project on Open Science Academy (OSCA; Poland - coordinator, plus Croatia, Italy, Portugal, and Germany). During the project, national communities learned from each other and at the same time embedded their own experiences into OPERAS showing intention on further collaboration, beyond OPERAS-PLUS.

The central event of the OPERAS-PLUS project was the [OPERAS Conference 2024](#) hosted by the University of Zadar, the Croatian national node (OPERAS-HR), which has gathered a vibrant community of open science enthusiasts.

Examples of National impact and integration during the project period:

During the project period, the visibility and reach of national initiatives enhanced. E.g., the Open Access Books Network (OABN) began as an informal network to foster dialogue around open access (OA) books. It was created by OAPEN, Open Book Publishers, and SPARC Europe—three members of OPERAS. These organisations are part of the UK and Dutch nodes of OPERAS: OPERAS-UK, led by Jisc, and OPERAS-NL,

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led by OAPEN. In 2023, this network became a Special Interest Group within the OPERAS research infrastructure. Since then, it has served a global community, connecting publishers, researchers, librarians, and infrastructure providers dedicated to equitable and accessible OA book publishing. Through activities such as workshops, webinars, blogs, and interactive discussion forums, the OABN has become a vital space for knowledge-sharing and best-practice development. By becoming part of OPERAS, OABN has gained greater visibility and now operates within a broader research infrastructure, which supports its connections to related projects and stakeholders, such as the Horizon Europe-funded PALOMERA project².

The construction of the Italian National Node, **OPERAS-IT**, has been an important development as it was constituted within a remarkably short period of 12 months, triggering a significant interest from other infrastructures, institutions and individuals to engage and commit with the consortium. The formation of H2IOSC (Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud), a project together with the national nodes of CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it and OPERAS-IT, is seeking to create a collaborative cluster of European distributed research infrastructures involved in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors with operating nodes across Italy. Besides that, the consortium made possible the organization of a successful technology event together with the Horizon Europe-funded CRAFT-OA project, where OPERAS is also involved.

In 2024, the Polish National Node, **OPERAS-PL (led by IBL PAN)** created a [Manifesto of Open Humanities](#) to mark the completion of its two-year project funded by the Polish Ministry (2022-2024). It initiated discussions on the role of open science in humanities research assessment within Poland. Through various events organised as part of OPERAS-PL's National Node activities, the need for clear guiding principles was highlighted and discussed with various stakeholders: research institutions, librarians, publishers and policy-makers. This manifesto serves as a call to action, advocating for including open science principles in research assessment, funding for publishers and investing in open scholarly communication infrastructure. In December 2024, OPERAS-PL was transformed into a consortium of 9 research organisations.

In Croatia, the **University of Zadar** serves as the National Node (**OPERAS-HR**), facilitating the implementation of European developments into institutional and national standards through more direct and streamlined access. For example, the

² PALOMERA – Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>. Grant agreement ID: 101094270

University Publishing Office is implementing standards and tools from DIAMAS and OPERAS services such as PRISM into its systems, and OPERAS-HR is advocating for European initiatives such as supporting the Barcelona Declaration. The same principle also applies to other national nodes.

National Nodes such as **OPERAS-PT** (the Portuguese node led by the **University of Coimbra**), are providing expertise for specific topics that are particularly important and addressing needs within the open scholarly communication community in the Social Sciences and Humanities. OPERAS-PT, for example, is contributing with its expertise on Multilingualism during the project period through its work as a leader of the Special Interest Group on Multilingualism of OPERAS. OPERAS-PT initiated the creation of a new translation service, *Mondaecus* with the purpose of supporting collaborative work that brings together translators, proofreaders and subject matter experts to deliver high-quality translations. Additionally, National Nodes have enabled translations for national communities early in the process, such as DOAS via the *Mondaecus* service. *Mondaecus* has earned the status of OPERAS Candidate Service, and is working on being onboarded into the OPERAS Service Catalogue.

The Slovenian national node **OPERAS-SI**, led by ZRC SAZU (Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts), was founded in December 2024 as a consortium of 6 members. It consists of three of the largest Slovenian universities, two SSH research institutions and the university library. All members of the consortium are also active in the Slovenian Open Science Community (SSOZ), which includes all relevant stakeholders (RPOs and RFOs), also from the STEM field. SSOZ has already entrusted OPERAS-SI with the coordination of activities related to publishing: How can the quality and visibility of academic publishing in Slovenia be increased? OPERAS-SI is currently compiling a list of Slovenian scientific journals (in conjunction with the activities of the project CRAFT-OA and the European Diamond Capacity Hub) and organising several workshops to promote the use of OJS. It is also expected that OPERAS-SI will be also financially supported by the Ministry in 2025 and that further events will be organised according to the needs of the community.

In March 2023, the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) joined OPERAS, simultaneously beginning the design of its activities as **OPERAS-ES**. This membership, driven by FECYT's role as a provider of public services for the diamond open access academic publishing system, opened the door for Spanish research institutions to join OPERAS as ordinary members. It is worth noting that FECYT operates in alignment with the National Strategy for Open Science (ENCA, in Spanish) and with recent legislative reforms supporting open science, enabling OPERAS-ES to function under the same framework and legal alignment as current Spanish policy.

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Sustainability

Each national community built a strong foundation for further growth after OPERAS-PLUS. In addition, within the OPERAS framework, national languages are also prioritised to enhance accessibility. For instance, the GoTriple and VERA services are available in 10 and 9 different languages respectively, those of the National Nodes, making resources more accessible for local users. National Nodes are also supporting the translation of information and presentation materials into their national languages. A [“Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes”](#), developed within WP7 of OPERAS-PLUS, provides a structure, a guide and a beacon for the establishment of the national communities that are critical for the reach of the Research Infrastructure objectives around the European Research Area (ERA). Additionally to that, each national node prepared their own roadmap and worked on building up their national communities.

OPERAS-PLUS supported national nodes during the monthly meetings opened to all national node representatives, and not only those represented in the project itself, in order to share crucial information, ensure mutual learning experience and get insights on the specificities of each country. National nodes representatives worked together on monthly meetings and in March of 2025, OPERAS decided to establish the National Nodes Committee, which will have its place in the future ERIC governance scheme.

Each community is unique, has its specificities and expertise, and OPERAS-PLUS encouraged each of them to pave their own path and to choose which will work for each of them. By supporting the national nodes via the National Nodes Committee meetings, OPERAS-PLUS ensured that each Node had support during the process of building national communities and sought to capture their activities. Even though each national node had the freedom to operate under the different levels of formalities and structures, representatives were encouraged to bring more stakeholders into their networks, to onboard their potential partners at the national level and to seek support from their Ministries and other governmental bodies.

3. Exploitation and dissemination in action

Throughout the OPERAS-PLUS project, dissemination and exploitation activities were not treated as separate outputs but embedded into the development, coordination, and sustainability planning of the project's results. The approach focused on ensuring that key outcomes would be visible, usable, and integrated into the long-term operations of the OPERAS infrastructure. This section provides an overview of how

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exploitation and dissemination were implemented in practice to support this objective.

Exploitation

Exploitation activities during OPERAS-PLUS focused on strengthening the long-term adoption and integration of project results within the OPERAS infrastructure and its broader community. Rather than having exploitation as a post-project phase, it was embedded into the ongoing coordination and tracking of each KER. Exploitation followed a structured logic, ensuring that each KER contributed to the long-term operationalisation of the infrastructure. The approach focused on integrating results into institutional processes, enabling their immediate use and future sustainability. Each KER built on the previous one, forming a coherent pathway from foundational frameworks to distributed adoption. Progress was monitored through the OPERAS-PLUS Confluence workspace and regular internal updates aligned with the evolving OPERAS strategies.

KER1 established foundations of the legal, financial, and governance frameworks required for OPERAS' transition to ERIC. Exploitation was achieved through formal adoption processes, including national consultations, the establishment of the BGR, and iterative discussion of the ERIC statutes, financial model, and risk management strategy within OPERAS' internal structures.

KER2 operationalised innovation management. The Innovation Lab developed workflows that are already in use in new projects (e.g. GRAPHIA, LUMEN). Exploitation was implemented by integrating the Lab as a functional coordination mechanism within OPERAS, enabling structured innovation support beyond the project scope.

KER3 consolidated OPERAS' service portfolio and implemented FitSM-based management practices. Exploitation focused on ensuring operational continuity through standardised service phases, performance monitoring, and sustainability planning. Several services transitioned into full production and are currently managed under this model.

KER4 developed a systematic approach to training aligned with OPERAS' service logic and FitSM-based management principles. Exploitation included the development of training design templates, and while formal adoption is expected post-project, the framework is designed for decentralised delivery by national nodes and service teams. It also supports compatibility with European skills initiatives, including FAIR-by-design and EOSC onboarding approaches.

KER5 reinforced exploitation at national level by enabling national nodes to assume formal and informal roles in dissemination, coordination, and policy interface. 13

national nodes were operational, with several launched or formalised through official national events. Nodes adopted OPERAS services, developed local roadmaps, and translated materials to support local communities. Some nodes coordinated or joined national and European projects. National nodes were also actively involved in preparing governance contributions for the future OPERAS ERIC through participation in monthly coordination meetings and the launch of the National Nodes Committee in March 2025.

This layered exploitation strategy ensured that results were not only reused but incorporated into OPERAS' long-term governance, services, and distributed engagement structures. It also ensured readiness for the ERIC transition, where all five KERs are expected to contribute actively.

Beyond individual KERs, exploitation activities also contributed to OPERAS' broader positioning by piloting organisational processes, building connections with external projects, defining internal operational models, and supporting the preparation of the ERIC application dossier. The overall approach to exploitation emphasised practical integration, flexibility, and iterative progress, recognising that sustainability would depend on a diversified strategy combining structural mechanisms, project-based funding, and community participation.

Dissemination

Dissemination activities throughout OPERAS-PLUS were designed to maximise visibility, engagement, and adoption of project results, both within the OPERAS community and the broader SSH ecosystem. Dissemination was embedded into the infrastructure's operational and governance structures, including National Nodes, Special Interest Groups, the Assembly of Commons, and the Scientific Advisory Board. These internal bodies played a key role in communicating results, promoting uptake, and aligning activities with stakeholder needs across the distributed network.

External dissemination was supported through multiple channels aimed at broader audiences. The OPERAS website and blog served as primary public-facing dissemination platforms, complemented by regular newsletters, multilingual policy briefs, targeted communication campaigns, and participation in public events such as webinars and workshops as well as organising events such as the OPERAS Conference. Selected outputs, including the Innovation Lab case study series and service portfolio updates, were highlighted through dedicated external dissemination efforts. OPERAS-PLUS also ensured presence on platforms, e.g. Zenodo and the Horizon Results Platform, to further extend visibility and accessibility.

Dissemination activities increasingly focused on supporting the transition from project

results to long-term infrastructure development, positioning key outcomes within strategic planning documents such as the OPERAS ERIC dossier and the evolving service ecosystem. This integrated approach helped reinforce OPERAS' visibility within the European research infrastructure landscape and laid the groundwork for sustained engagement beyond the project's duration.

Dissemination in OPERAS-PLUS followed a result-driven model aligned with the development and uptake needs of each Key Exploitable Result (KER). The approach was differentiated and decentralised: each KER engaged specific audiences and channels based on its function and maturity. Each KER mobilised targeted dissemination pathways adapted to its function and audience: KER1 engaged stakeholders and national authorities to support the ERIC transition; KER2 activated communities and internal working groups to consolidate innovation capacity; KER3 addressed service users and technical partners through coordinated service dissemination and onboarding; KER4 focused on communities to support capacity building; KER5 relied on national structures and policy-facing actors to strengthen OPERAS' local presence. This KER-level embedding ensured that dissemination contributed not just to visibility, but to the operational integration and future sustainability of each result.

This decentralised structure was framed and supported by OPERAS' broader communication strategy, which provided shared identity, narrative consistency, and long-term positioning for the infrastructure. While dissemination was driven by the logic of the results, the communication layer helped ensure coherence across efforts, extending OPERAS' visibility through multilingual outreach, coordinated messaging, and cross-project alignment. Strategic communication and monitoring aspects will be further addressed in Deliverables D8.6 (Communication Strategy and Toolkit – Final) and D8.7 (Impact Monitoring Dashboard – Final), to be submitted in Month 36. These outputs complement the dissemination practices described above and will provide operational tools and metrics to sustain engagement beyond the lifetime of OPERAS-PLUS.

As OPERAS prepares for ERIC status, the practices embedded in OPERAS-PLUS will continue to mature into operational routines. The exploitation and dissemination frameworks will evolve into implementation protocols and collaborative workflows aligned with future needs.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is addressed in line with the OPERAS-PLUS Consortium Agreement and has been considered throughout the lifecycle of the project. Although IPR was not a dominant issue for most KERs, its

relevance was monitored on a case-by-case basis and reflected in the business and sustainability planning where appropriate. A general framework for IPR handling was included in earlier deliverables, and no specific conflicts or claims arose during the project.

4. Future Integration

The implementation of the PEDR has been instrumental in supporting OPERAS' maturation and in ensuring that results are not only documented but activated and sustained. As OPERAS prepares for the ERIC application process, the approaches to exploitation and dissemination developed through OPERAS-PLUS will continue to evolve. Future activities will be carried forward through organisational development, sustained engagement, and ongoing alignment efforts with EU research infrastructure initiatives such as EOSC. In parallel, the project's KERs will continue to inform future service development and community-facing strategies within the OPERAS ecosystem. OPERAS national nodes play a key role in the process of building national communities and spreading values of OPERAS. The core activities of OPERAS are embedded in the communities, OPERAS services are built with the community and for the community, and the network will continue to grow beyond the OPERAS-PLUS project.

2025 will be a critical year for OPERAS, as shown in the service roadmap because the majority of services will be in the production phase. This will require not only a focus on continual service improvement and marketing, but on sustainability as well.

As mentioned, OPERAS is exploring additional sustainability pathways, including service-specific strategies aligned with the principles of public mission support. Potential approaches under consideration include value-added services, freemium models, white-label adaptations, and enhanced project-based collaborations, always respecting the fundamental commitment to open scholarly communication and public good provision. New projects such as GRAPHIA, LUMEN, and FASCA are already contributing practical use cases, technical enhancements, and additional resources to reinforce the service ecosystem, with further opportunities being pursued through upcoming funding calls.

Through the legal entity, OPERAS AISBL ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its activities and services, as well as the effective collaboration and coordination of its members and partners. The AISBL status also enables OPERAS to engage in partnerships and collaborations with other organisations and stakeholders and to represent the interests of the SSH research community at the European and international levels.

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However, as OPERAS is transitioning towards becoming an ERIC, current financial and sustainability planning is being defined. Active collaboration is ongoing to ensure that all services are taken into consideration, both current and future. A cost analysis was refined as part of the ESFRI questionnaire update, which is helping to understand total costs and forecasting and is currently being discussed as part of both the OPERAS EA for short-term needs as well as the OPERAS BGR for medium to longer term.

Finally, OPERAS is participating in a number of EC-funded projects. To ensure organisational, technical and financial sustainability, projects aim to identify Key Exploitable Results (KER) with legal and administrative options that can provide the long-term sustainability of each KER. The OPERAS AISBL and wider RI, is often seen as a potential channel to be explored; however, sometimes sustainability strategies need to be coordinated across a variety of projects and activities. Something that has already been taken advantage of with the GoTriple service as one of the main KERs from the TRIPLE project as well as the VERA service resulting from the COESO project, where OPERAS serves as the legal host while also supporting the agreement structure. Though it does not necessarily have to be the mechanism that is used, it represents the possibility for KER to be continuously exploited where needed.

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Annex

To ensure clarity and avoid duplication in the main body of the report, all supporting tables and structured information related to the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) have been moved to this Annex. The annex includes both the tables formatted in accordance with the Horizon Results Platform requirements and a series of internal project tables that were previously included directly in D8.3 and D8.4. These internal materials cover dissemination activities, performance indicators, action plans, and structured progress summaries associated with each KER. The content was compiled and maintained throughout the project, primarily through the OPERAS-PLUS Confluence environment and other coordination tools, and reflects the final, consolidated status of each KER. Presenting this material in a separate annex allows for a more focused narrative in the main report while ensuring completeness and transparency in documenting the project's dissemination and exploitation efforts.

The tables included in this annex reflect the status of each KER at the time of report preparation. As the PEDR has functioned as a living document, updates and adjustments compared to earlier versions are to be expected. While most Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined at the beginning of the project proved useful for internal tracking and reporting, a limited number were found to be insufficiently informative or not applicable in practice. In such cases, the indicators were excluded, but this decision does not affect the overall integrity of the results.

KER1: OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework

1.1. Internal Overview

KER Overview

KER #	KER1
KER Full Name	OPERAS core governance, finance, and management framework
KER Description	The OPERAS core governance, finance, and management Framework (KER1) encompasses the foundational elements necessary for transitioning OPERAS into a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). This KER includes the development and implementation of various models and policies such as governance, financial sustainability, human resources, risk management, and capacity planning. The aim is to ensure that OPERAS strengthens as a robust and

	sustainable research infrastructure, facilitating open scholarly communication within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).
Related WP#	WP2 OPERAS construction phase framework development
KER Champion	Yannick Legré
Type	Other Tangible
Target Audience	Internal and external stakeholders

KER objectives and expected results

This KER covers the overarching governance and sustainability of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure as it moves towards becoming an ERIC. Therefore the individual results are combined into a single KER with dedicated exploitation plans as follows:

- The compliance and/or certification of the OPERAS ERIC with quality, IT service and risk management ISO standards.
- An initial legal framework and financial multiannual plan to prepare for the transition towards an ERIC.
- Updated governance model, including relationships with private and commercial entities.
- Prototype and update of the Business Model to support the long-term sustainability of OPERAS.
- An equal opportunity pan-European employment framework with a specific focus on the gender equality plan, including the applicability of RESAVER³.
- Develop and implement a risk management framework and capacity plan.
- Update medium and long-term strategic plans.

KER Dissemination Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	Achieved total (May 2025)	Percentage
Engage internal stakeholders in the process and activities for OPERAS becoming an ERIC	ONGOING	AoC, STB, EA, GA and SAC	5	5	100%

³ <https://www.resaver.eu/>

Develop draft statutes in preparation for the ERIC	ONGOING	Statutes agreed	1	1	100%
Strengthen commitment of existing OPERAS GA members in the new OPERAS ERIC preparation	ONGOING	Countries represented in the BGR	15	12 ⁴	80%
Onboarding new countries in the General Assembly	ONGOING	Countries represented in the GA	5	3	60%

KER Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
ERIC Statutes and legal documents submitted to the EC for approval	Prepare OPERAS ERIC governance model	Initial OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.1)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Updated OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.5)	REMOVED	N/A
		Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy	M36	SENSITIVE

⁴ BGR was created in late November 2023

		Implementation Plan (D2.8)		
	Prepare legal and financial framework of OPERAS ERIC	Initial OPERAS Legal & Financial framework (D2.2)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Submit the draft OPERAS ERIC statutes to the EC (D3.3)	M36	SENSITIVE
	Risk and Capacity	OPERAS risk management framework and capacity plan - Initial (D2.4)	M15	SENSITIVE
		OPERAS risk management framework and capacity plan – Final (D2.7)	M33	
	Define human resources framework	Initial OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.3)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Final OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.6)	M36	SENSITIVE

1.2 Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	Cascading OPERAS core governance, finance, and management framework for building a sustainable research infrastructure in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to the national nodes
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*Message / Teaser to potential user	Not applicable
*Video/Image	Not applicable
*Result type	Select only 1
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other - please specify in the Result Description.
*EU Missions	Select any that apply
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation to climate change Cancer Climate-neutral and smart cities Oceans, seas, and waters Soil health and food Not applicable

*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>	
	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants and Subsidies • Loans • Loan guarantees • Other blended financing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations • Incubators / Accelerators • Marketing Mentoring or Coaching • Financing Expertise • Technology Transfer Expertise • Legal / IPR advise • I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party • Investor readiness training • Investor introductions 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business plan development • Expanding to more markets /finding new customers • Executive Training • Other type of Investment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Technology Organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia/Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Angels • Venture Capital • Crowd-funding Equity • Other type of Investment
*We specifically need / are looking for (600 characters max)		

About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	OPERAS members; National communities
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: OPERAS website

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	Link: https://operas-eu.org/
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	All national nodes use our templates	
*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Please select up to three	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy ● Environment ● EU enlargement ● European neighbourhood policy ● Food safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport ● Statistics ● Taxation ● Trade ● Transport ● Youth

*Tags / Keywords		
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	<p>Please select up to three</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal 1: No poverty ● Goal 2: Zero hunger ● Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people ● Goal 4: Quality education ● Goal 5: Gender equality ● Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation ● Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy ● Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth ● Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure ● Goal 10: Reducing inequalities ● Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities ● Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production ● Goal 13: Climate action ● Goal 14: Life below water ● Goal 15: Life on land ● Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions ● Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals ● Not applicable 	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No 	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) ● 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) ● 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) ● 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) ● 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) • 7 - Market Deployment • Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	Not applicable
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	
Do you have a scalable business model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.

Investors Corner

<p>*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?</p>	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <100K • 101-500K • 501K-1M • 1M-2.5M • 2.6M-5M • 5.1M-10M • >10M • No investment sought
<p>I can provide the following upon request by an interested party</p>	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentation(s) • Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) • Case study(ies) • Related Technology white paper • A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators • List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) • A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers • Complete and detailed business plan • Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? • Quantitative Assessment • Qualitative Assessment • Competitive Assessment • List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") • List of investors

KER2: OPERAS Innovation Lab

2.1. Internal Overview

KER Overview

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KER #	KER2
KER Full Name	OPERAS Innovation Lab
KER Description	OPERAS Innovation Lab is a support mechanism for innovating scholarly communication in SSH. Its goal is to assist researchers, companies and scholarly institutions in planning and developing novel and/or improved solutions. The OPERAS Innovation Lab provides support to its stakeholders through innovation observatory and accelerator and through activities such as innovation management and innovation research and assessment.
Related WP#	WP4 OPERAS Innovation Lab development
KER Champion	Maciej Maryl, Tomasz Umerle
Type	SCIENTIFIC OR TECH R&D ICT SOFTWARE DIGITAL SOLUTION
Target Audience	Internal and external stakeholders

KER objectives and expected results

The general objective is to establish the OPERAS Innovation Lab as the knowledge hub and support mechanism for the OPERAS community, providing guidelines and counselling to stakeholders wishing to engage with innovative outputs, and liaising with those stakeholders, relevant e-infrastructure providers and the private sector. The further objectives are to:

- Structure the Innovation Lab within OPERAS by establishing working relationships with OPERAS members and other e-infrastructure providers, who may offer services for innovative and FAIR outputs.
- Provide coherent and up-to-date knowledge on innovations to the OPERAS community.
- Support and sustain innovative outputs in SSH disciplines.
- Strengthen the prestige of innovative publications through prototyping their evaluation.

KER Dissemination Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	Achieved total (May 2025)	Percentage
# of blog posts and	M1-36	researchers, companies,	30	26	86%

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case studies on the observatory		academic institutions			
# of presentations	M1-36	researchers, companies, academic institutions	10	10	100%

KER Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 2: Empowering Community	O9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab	# of calls run through the innovation lab	2	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of blog posts on the observatory	9	IBL PAN
		# of new services proposed to the OPERAS service portfolio	1	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of new pilot proposals submitted	3	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of case studies	4	IBL PAN

KER Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
The Innovation Lab is defined	Set up internal research seminar	Seminar held	DONE	
	Prepare the Innovation Lab Terms of Reference (ToR)	ToR presented to STB	IN PROGRESS	Lab is a standing agenda point
WP4 outputs have been delivered	Guidelines on publishing and evaluating innovative outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities	D4.1 submitted (M27)	ACHIEVED	10.5281/zenodo.14221728

	Organise community validation workshop	MS7 (M16)	ACHIEVED	OPERAS Conf'24 Workshop 2nd
An OPERAS Innovation fund is set-up	Define the scope and the budget envelope of the innovation fund	Included in end of year budget	IN PROGRESS	
	Communicate about the Innovation Fund	TBD	PLANNED FOR 2025	
	Launch call(s) for participation	TBD	PLANNED FOR 2025	

2.2 Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS Innovation Lab: Supporting Great Ideas for Open Communication in SSH
*Message / Teaser to potential user	OPERAS Innovation Lab is a support mechanism for scholarly communication in SSH. Its goal is to assist researchers, companies and scholarly institutions in planning and developing novel and/or improved solutions. OPERAS Innovation Lab provides support to its stakeholders through innovation observatory, innovation management and innovation research and assessment.
*Video/Image	(tbd)
*Result type	Select only 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.). Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be

5

<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/conference-workshops-details/#workshop-2>

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	<p>a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development. 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other - please specify in the Result Description. 	
*EU Missions	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation to climate change • Cancer • Climate-neutral and smart cities • Oceans, seas, and waters • Soil health and food • Not applicable 	
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>	
	<p>Target audiences (up to 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers 	<p>Our Needs (any that apply)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grants and Subsidies Loans Loan guarantees Other blended financing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations Incubators / Accelerators Marketing Mentoring or Coaching Financing Expertise Technology Transfer Expertise Legal / IPR advise I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party Investor readiness training Investor introductions Business plan development Expanding to more markets /finding new customers Executive Training Other type of Investment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and Technology Organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help in technical expertise Use of research Infrastructure Collaboration

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia/Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help in technical expertise Use of research Infrastructure Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private Investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business Angels Venture Capital Crowd-funding Equity Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	<p>We are looking for innovators in the SSH field who either want to showcase their work through the OPERAS channels or who seek help in developing their ideas, concepts or services through collaboration with the Lab's network. Additionally, we are looking for researchers, experts performing research on innovation to help us better understand innovation mechanism and the role of innovation evaluation.</p>	

About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	<p>OPERAS AISBL IBL PAN OAPEN UNIZD UNITO CNRS DARIAH</p>
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description:
	Link:
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

<p>*Result description (1200 characters max)</p>	<p>OPERAS Innovation Lab will be an OPERAS service which deals with innovation observation, management and research. Embedded in the OPERAS organisation, it is being designed as a mechanism which allows a diverse SSH community of researchers, institutions and companies to collaborate and build networks which lead to development of successful, sustainable and exploitable SSH innovations.</p>	
<p>*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy ● Environment ● EU enlargement ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport ● Statistics ● Taxation ● Trade ● Transport 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European neighbourhood policy • Food safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth
*Tags / Keywords	innovation Innovation science management ideas management pilot acceleration R&D	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal 1: No poverty • Goal 2: Zero hunger • Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people • Goal 4: Quality education • Goal 5: Gender equality • Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation • Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy • Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth • Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure • Goal 10: Reducing inequalities • Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities • Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production • Goal 13: Climate action • Goal 14: Life below water • Goal 15: Life on land • Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions • Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals • Not applicable 	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	Please select one <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) ● 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) ● 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) ● 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) ● 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) ● 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) ● 7 - Market Deployment ● Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	OPERAS Innovation Lab is in the process of working on a selected number of case studies (5 innovations from the SSH community) which will allow it to iteratively shape and test its processes designed to observe, support and evaluate SSH innovation.
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	OPERAS Innovation lab aims to provide a professionalised mechanism for the SSH community to engage with the OPERAS ESFRI as a key innovation actor in the SSH. It will offer support in innovation management and provide access to innovation ecosystem of OPERAS consisting of a rich service catalogue and a network of researchers, institutions and companies.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	now or at the end of the project?
Is your result replicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	now or at the end of the project?

Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	now or at the end of the project?
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.
	Europe South America

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Please select one
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <100K • 101-500K • 501K-1M • 1M-2.5M • 2.6M-5M • 5.1M-10M • >10M • No investment sought
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	Select any that apply
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentation(s) • Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) • Case study(ies) • Related Technology white paper • A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators • List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) • A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers • Complete and detailed business plan

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? ● Quantitative Assessment ● Qualitative Assessment ● Competitive Assessment ● List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") ● List of investors
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KER3: OPERAS portfolio of services

3.1. Internal Overview

KER Overview

KER #	KER3
KER Full Name	OPERAS portfolio of services
KER Description	OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services are grouped into eight categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.
Related WP#	WP5 Technical support to OPERAS services
KER Champion	Sy Holsinger
Type	SERVICES
Target Audience	SSH Researchers; Authors; Editors, Editorial Managers; Publishers; Libraries; Translators

KER Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

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Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 2: Empowering community Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	Services	# of services in a catalogue	6	OPERAS AISBL
		# of services in a portfolio	12	
	Business models for Services	# of services with a clearly defined business model	3	
	FitSM	# of FitSM training courses held	24	
		# of personal FitSM certifications	300+	

KER Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
OPERAS Integrated Management System initial version operational	Create initial structure	N/A	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/home
	Provide access to relevant members	Instructions circulated to relevant mailing lists	DONE	158 ACTIVE USERS
	Populate with initial content	D5.1 (M12)	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/home
Service strategy and roadmap published	Publish an annual service strategy and roadmap	Draft version available for STB in Sept 2024	DONE	6-7 May EA F2F (Paris) + STB 14 May
Business models for all current and new services (incl. licensing models) established	Service Design and Transition Packages (SDTP) available for all services	D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5 (M12)	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/OPERAS/pages/884870/Service+Design+and+Transition+Packages+SDTP

Service reviews, including capacity requirements (e.g. sustainability) conducted	Prepare service review template	Q3 2024	NOT DONE	
	Conduct service review	Q4 2024	DONE	OCT F2F Dec 2024 (Brussels)
FitSM organisation certification achieved and retained	Conduct initial IMS Maturity Assessment	Q4 2024	FUTURE ACTION	Postponed as part of the 2026-2028 Strategic Plan
	Conduct internal audit of OPERAS Integrated management system	Q2 2025	FUTURE ACTION	Postponed as part of the 2026-2028 Strategic Plan
	Conduct certification audit against FitSM	Q1 2026	FUTURE ACTION	Postponed as part of the 2026-2028 Strategic Plan

3.2 Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS portfolio of services
*Message / Teaser to potential user	OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services are grouped into eight categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.
*Video/Image	
*Result type	Select only 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex.

	<p>regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness. ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development. Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.) Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.). Other - please specify in the Result Description.
*EU Missions	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation to climate change Cancer Climate-neutral and smart cities Oceans, seas, and waters Soil health and food Not applicable
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>

	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants and Subsidies • Loans • Loan guarantees • Other blended financing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations • Incubators / Accelerators • Marketing Mentoring or Coaching • Financing Expertise • Technology Transfer Expertise • Legal / IPR advise • I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party • Investor readiness training • Investor introductions • Business plan development • Expanding to more markets /finding new customers • Executive Training • Other type of Investment

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Technology Organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia/Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Angels • Venture Capital • Crowd-funding Equity • Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	Increase usage/uptake of services; Financial support	

About us

Other related projects	COESO, TRIPLE, ATRIUM
*Result Contributors	OPERAS AISBL, Ubiquity Press, Net7, Lexis, OAPEN, UC
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: Service Catalogue
	Link: https://operas-eu.org/services/
	Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Bluesky, YouTube

Result Description and Influence

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

<p>*Result description (1200 characters max)</p>	<p>OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services are grouped into eight categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.</p>	
<p>*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy ● Environment ● EU enlargement ● European neighbourhood policy ● Food safety ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport ● Statistics ● Taxation ● Trade ● Transport ● Youth 	
<p>*Tags / Keywords</p>	<p>SSH, Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, Collaboration Tools, Metrics,</p>	

	Peer-Review, Diamond, Open Access, Publishing, Citizen Science, Participatory Research	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal 1: No poverty ● Goal 2: Zero hunger ● Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people ● Goal 4: Quality education ● Goal 5: Gender equality ● Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation ● Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy ● Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth ● Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure ● Goal 10: Reducing inequalities ● Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities ● Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production ● Goal 13: Climate action ● Goal 14: Life below water ● Goal 15: Life on land ● Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions ● Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals ● Not applicable 	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No 	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	Please select one	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) ● 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) ● 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) ● 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) ● 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) ● 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) ● 7 - Market Deployment ● Not applicable 	

*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	All services have recently moved from a variety of development phases into production. Moving forward, we are shifting our focus towards marketing and sustainability. This transition brings about exciting opportunities for growth and expansion. However, it also poses challenges, particularly in ensuring the long-term sustainability of our services.
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	A comprehensive approach supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	Though it would be a challenge for organisations to copy what has been done, there is an opportunity to replicate a couple services in terms of offering a white label solution.
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	OPERAS Research Infrastructure provides a sustainable structure for managing the service portfolio in the long-term. However, ensuring the long-term financing is still under discussion alongside the preparations to become an ERIC. Current financial commitments are on an annual basis. Some project funding will need to be sought in order to bridge the gap.
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.

Investors Corner

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<p>*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?</p>	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <100K • 101-500K • 501K-1M • 1M-2.5M • 2.6M-5M • 5.1M-10M • >10M • No investment sought
<p>I can provide the following upon request by an interested party</p>	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentation(s) • Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) • Case study(ies) • Related Technology white paper • A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators • List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) • A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers • Complete and detailed business plan • Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? • Quantitative Assessment • Qualitative Assessment • Competitive Assessment • List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") • List of investors

KER4: OPERAS user training framework

4.1. Internal Overview

KER Overview

KER #	KER4
KER Full Name	OPERAS user training framework

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KER Description	The OPERAS User Training Framework provides a systematic and modular approach to user training, skills development and capacity building, tailored to the needs of the SSH community and the wider scholarly communication ecosystem. Developed under Task 6.4 of OPERAS-PLUS (M20-M36), the Framework acts as an umbrella and coordination mechanism for existing OPERAS-related training activities provided by projects such as TRIPLE, COESO, DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, EDCH and Skills4EOSC. It aims to support the integration of training as a cross-cutting, service-enabling function within OPERAS, in line with FitSM principles, and proposes quality management mechanisms, KPIs and user engagement workflows that could inform future formal adoption within the OPERAS Service Management System (SMS).
Related WP#	WP6 User engagement and training
KER Champion	Franjo Pehar
Type	SERVICES
Target Audience	Academia/Universities; Research and Technology Organisations: EU and Member State Policymakers

KER Dissemination Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	Achieved total (May 2025)	Percentage
Awareness raising through OPERAS communication channels (presentations, papers, poster, blog posts, newsletters)	M20-M36	4	2	0	Planned for M32-M36
Internal consultation and presentations to working groups, SIGs and national nodes	M24-M36	4	2	0	Planned for M32-M36

Publication and dissemination of the final framework (e.g. D6.3, summary materials, training toolkit)	M36	1	1	0	IN PROGRESS
Presentation of the framework at OPERAS annual or major stakeholder events	Yearly	2	0	0	FUTURE ACTION)
# of participants attending FitSM training sessions organised by OPERAS	Quarterly/ Yearly	75	TBD	57	76%
# of views and downloads of the UCQ-FRAME document from the Zenodo platform.	Yearly	300 views 150 downloads	230 180	363 views 216 downloads	+100% +100%

KER Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Note: The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) listed below are designed to be implemented and monitored after the formal delivery of the OPERAS User Training Framework (D6.3, due M36). They reflect post-project objectives aimed at supporting the long-term integration of the Training Framework into the OPERAS service portfolio and governance structures.

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 2: Empowering community	To increase the adoption and implementation of the training framework	Number of OPERAS services and national nodes delivering training using	Annual reporting from OPERAS nodes and services	OCT and national node managers

	by OPERAS services and national nodes.	the framework.		
Pillar 2: Empowering community	To promote community-led training design and adaptation.	Number of community-led training events using framework templates or guidelines	Submission of reports or event descriptions tagged with framework references	Service providers, National nodes,
Pillar 2: Empowering community	Strengthen internal service readiness through FitSM certification.	Number of FitSM trainings conducted and individuals certified # of FitSM training courses held # of personal FitSM certifications	Course attendance records, certification records 5 57	OPERAS AISBL
Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	To promote the localisation and multilingual adaptation of training resources.	Number of framework-based training resources translated/adapted for national or disciplinary contexts.	Deposits in OPERAS training materials repository, reporting by SIGs or nodes	SIGs, national nodes, service teams
Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	To embed quality assurance in the design and delivery of training.	Proportion of training events using at least one template/articl	Post-training reports including completed framework templates	Training organisers, OPERAS training coordination team

		e from the framework.		
Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	To evaluate the effectiveness of training using standardised user feedback tools.	Number of training events evaluated using standardised OPERAS feedback forms (e.g. satisfaction, usefulness, applicability).	Completed participant feedback forms, aggregated metrics	Training organisers, OPERAS training coordination team

KER Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
Developed OPERAS Training strategy	Identification of relevant training areas	D6.3 (M36)	DONE	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1L4Sn5Ru3zhhQD9MyIDoeecYZrD0p3rgZDbL9oSTYjw/edit#slide=id.g2cd97972bba_0_260
	Identification of relevant targeted user groups	D6.3 (M36)	DONE	
	Identification of opportunities for facilitating and performing training	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
	Identification of training providers	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
	Description of training activities	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	

Designed Competence Center for Social Sciences and Humanities	Preparation of Open Science, FAIR and RDM learning path for SSH	SKILLS4EOSC D5.2	DUE AUG 2025	https://ssh-tot-fair-by-design.gitlab.io/OS-RDM-SSH/atest
	Recommendation of actions for the set-up of Open Science and RDM thematic trainings	SKILLS4EOSC D5.6	DUE AUG 2025	
Integrated dissemination of Knowledge into OPERAS Communication	Common framework defining the methodology for achieving user-centred quality objectives (D6.1)	D6.1 (M10)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/8081977
	Report on implementation of the methodological framework for user-centred quality on selected services	MS6 (M14)	DONE	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1adDEIMV1bLqjNTmoDLLKwzx6JqUcxSZe/view
		D6.2 (M30)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/14935954
		MS10 (M32)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/15340523
Framework for the development of open science and scholarly communication training	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS		

Knowledge acquired in IT Service Management using FitSM (lightweight ITSM standard) as the reference framework	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	FitSM included in published version	IN PROGRESS	
	Identify (new) opportunities for organising training courses	CONTINUOUS	IN PROGRESS	i.e. https://operas-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/FitSM-FND-Overview-Agenda_23Apr2024_OPERAS-Conf24.docx.pdf
	Organise courses	1 per year (min)	DONE	https://operas-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/FitSM-FND-Overview-Agenda_23Apr2024_OPERAS-Conf24.docx.pdf
Knowledge acquired on the individual services offered by OPERAS	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	DONE	Internal doc
	Conduct webinars and/or hands-on trainings	1 per service per year	DONE	e.g. PRISM ⁶ , VERA ⁷

⁶ <https://youtu.be/XMnsZqWcKGA?si=KN6pQOhGgLSjGvnl>

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9hXxmDpd5kM>

OPERAS services alignment with EOSC and FAIR requirements webinar or presentation	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	IN PROGRESS	
	Conduct webinars or presentation	1 workshop for the service providers held	PLANNED FOR 2025	
OPERAS Integrated Management System for Federation Members webinar and/or presentation	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	DONE	Internal doc
	Conduct webinars or presentation	Webinar held	PLANNED FOR 2025	

4.1. Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS User Training Framework for Open Science and Scholarly Communication in SSH
*Message / Teaser to potential user	<p>“OPERAS User Training Framework for Open Science and Scholarly Communication in SSH”</p> <p>The OPERAS User Training Framework supports research infrastructures, service providers and training coordinators with ready-to-use tools and guidance to design and deliver modular, FAIR-by-design training in scholarly communication, Diamond Open Access publishing, research data management, EOSC onboarding and participatory research. Developed with and for the SSH community, but adaptable to different contexts across Europe.</p>
*Video/Image	

*Result type	Select only 1	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.). 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness. 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development. 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Intangible Results – (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services – (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.). 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other - please specify in the Result Description. 	
*EU Missions	Select any that apply	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation to climate change Cancer Climate-neutral and smart cities Oceans, seas, and waters Soil health and food Not applicable 	
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>	
	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants and Subsidies • Loans • Loan guarantees • Other blended financing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations • Incubators / Accelerators • Marketing Mentoring or Coaching • Financing Expertise • Technology Transfer Expertise • Legal / IPR advise • I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party • Investor readiness training • Investor introductions • Business plan development • Expanding to more markets /finding new customers • Executive Training • Other type of Investment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Technology Organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia/Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Angels • Venture Capital • Crowd-funding Equity • Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	<p>We seek opportunities to collaborate with research infrastructures, open science initiatives and training providers to pilot, adopt or adapt the OPERAS User Training Framework. We seek feedback, alignment with national and European skills strategies, and contributions to community-led delivery models that ensure long-term sustainability, multilingual reach, and responsiveness to SSH-specific training needs.</p>	

About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	UNIZD, OPERAS AISBL, UNITO, AMU, Lexis, Net7, OAPEN, Ubiquity Press
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description:
	Link:
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	<p>The OPERAS User Training Framework provides a structured and modular approach to user training, skills development and capacity building across the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and scholarly communication ecosystem. Developed as part of the</p>
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	<p>OPERAS-PLUS project, it coordinates and complements existing training provided by OPERAS-related projects (TRIPLE, COESO, DIAMAS, EDCH, Skills4EOSC). It supports the transition of OPERAS to an ERIC by proposing how training can be integrated as a cross-cutting, service-enabling activity. The framework includes FAIR-by-design training materials, structured templates, decentralised delivery models and alignment with fitSM-based service management. It promotes multilingual, community-led and sustainable training practices and aligns with broader European open science skills initiatives, including EOSC. The framework is designed for reuse and adaptation by services, infrastructures and training providers in SSH and beyond.</p>			
<p>*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="485 920 1369 1908"> <tr> <td data-bbox="485 920 928 1908"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy </td> <td data-bbox="928 920 1369 1908"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport </td> </tr> </table>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture and rural development ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foreign affairs and security policy ● Fraud prevention ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environment ● EU enlargement ● European neighbourhood policy ● Food safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Statistics ● Taxation ● Trade ● Transport ● Youth
<p>*Tags / Keywords</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Science ● Scholarly Communication ● Diamond Open Access ● SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) ● Research Data Management (RDM) ● FAIR Principles ● Capacity Building ● User Training ● fitSM ● Citizen Science ● Community Led Training ● OPERAS 	
<p>*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal 1: No poverty ● Goal 2: Zero hunger ● Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people ● Goal 4: Quality education ● Goal 5: Gender equality ● Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation ● Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy ● Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth ● Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure ● Goal 10: Reducing inequalities ● Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities ● Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production ● Goal 13: Climate action ● Goal 14: Life below water ● Goal 15: Life on land ● Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions ● Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals ● Not applicable 	

Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) • 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) • 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) • 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) • 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) • 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) • 7 - Market Deployment • Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	<p>The framework is in advanced development under Task 6.4 of OPERAS-PLUS, with pilot training activities completed and testing/validation scheduled for June 2025. Final delivery is planned for August 2025 (D6.3). Next steps include stakeholder consultation, refinement and alignment with OPERAS governance for potential long-term adoption.</p>
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	<p>A modular FAIR-by-design training framework to support community-led scholarly communication, including Diamond Open Access publishing, research data management and EOSC alignment - designed for decentralised delivery and integration into the OPERAS service governance and future ERIC model.</p>

Do you have a scalable business model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • <input checked="" type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	<p>OPERAS User Training Framework is designed to be fully replicable and adaptable across different research infrastructures, institutional contexts and disciplinary domains. Its modular structure and FAIR-by-design learning materials allow other communities to adopt, adapt and implement the framework based on their own user needs, service priorities and governance models. The toolkit approach - with templates for training design, delivery and evaluation - enables autonomous use by service teams and trainers. In addition, decentralised delivery models supported by national nodes, special interest groups (SIGs) and partners ensure localisation and scalability. Alignment with FitSM and EOOSC principles further supports cross-infrastructure compatibility and sustainability.</p>
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes • No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	<p>The OPERAS User Training Framework has been designed with long-term sustainability in mind. It builds on existing training capacity, outputs and infrastructure developed through OPERAS related projects such as TRIPLE, DIAMAS, COESO, EDCH and Skills4EOOSC. Its alignment with FitSM principles and OPERAS' emerging Service Management System (SMS) ensures future compatibility with internal quality management and service operations. The framework promotes decentralised, community-led delivery through national nodes and SIGs, fostering shared ownership and responsiveness to evolving needs. Training materials will</p>

	be developed as FAIR-by-design resources to maximise re-use and interoperability. The modular toolkit supports autonomous use by service teams, reducing reliance on central coordination. Sustainability will be further supported through integration with wider European open science initiatives and competence centres (e.g. Skills4EOSC).
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.
	Europe (open and inclusive approach, welcoming collaboration and engagement from the global scholarly community)

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Please select one
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <100K • 101-500K • 501K-1M • 1M-2.5M • 2.6M-5M • 5.1M-10M • >10M • No investment sought
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	Select any that apply
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentation(s) • Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) • Case study(ies) • Related Technology white paper • A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators • List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers • Complete and detailed business plan • Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? • Quantitative Assessment • Qualitative Assessment • Competitive Assessment • List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") • List of investors
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KER5: OPERAS national nodes

5.1. Internal Overview

KER Overview

KER #	KER5
KER Full Name	OPERAS national nodes
KER Description	National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level.
Related WP#	WP7 Support to national nodes
KER Champion	Delfim Leão
Type	OTHER INTANGIBLE
Target Audience	OPERAS Members; Special Interest Groups (SIGs) members; national communities (researchers, publishers, librarians, etc); OPERAS services target users; research policy-makers and funding organisations; European Research Infrastructures

KER Dissemination Activities

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Description	Timeframe	Target ⁸	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage	2024
Visitors on OPERAS website	2023	26,000	TBD	27,811	+100%	38.320
Followers on social media	2023	4,000	TBD	4,533 (1,064 new in 2023)	+100%	5515
Social media posts	2023	500	TBD	587 posts across all networks (X, LinkedIn, FB, Instagram)	+100%	903
Blog posts	2023	20	TBD	23	+100%	31

KER Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data
Pillar 1: Redesigning ecosystem	O1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly	New members (per country, European and non-European, ordinary)	4 (University of Lorraine, University of Rennes, Library University of Cyprus, CSIC)
		New national nodes/new member countries	3 new core member countries Spain, Norway, Finland (FECYT, ERIH+, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies)
		Days of engagement events	17 hours of self-organised events from the OPERAS national nodes

⁸ Targets to be updated as 100% has already been achieved

KER Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
Established OPERAS national nodes for each member of the EA	Sharing good practices	Internal WP Kick-off meeting with prospective national nodes (MS2)	DONE	Internal agenda
	National node can be used as regional node when needed and no linguistic barriers exist	Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes (D7.1)	DONE	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10725785
		Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes (D7.2)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/8289238
		Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes – Final (D7.3)	DUE MAY 2025	
	Formalising and securing relations between OPERAS hub and the nodes	Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)	DUE MAY 2025	
	Aligning Hub and national node governance	Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)	DUE AUG 2025	

5.2. Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	Establishment of a roadmap for the OPERAS national nodes
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*Message / Teaser to potential user	The set up of a roadmap has been agreed by all partners involved in the OPERAS-PLUS project and reviewed by external experts. Its utility is self-evident as a means for putting into practice activities to be carried out in nodes in all contexts and with different levels of funding and engagement. The purpose to make it public is to provide tools for other projects to implement their own nodes using this basis and adapting for their own realities. Our target audiences are all scientific communities and research infrastructures, especially those focused in the SSH.
*Video/Image	https://youtu.be/xf0VAJfPNpk
*Result type	Select only 1
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other - please specify in the Result Description.
*EU Missions	Select any that apply
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation to climate change

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cancer • Climate-neutral and smart cities • Oceans, seas, and waters • Soil health and food • Not applicable 										
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>										
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Target audiences (up to 3)</th> <th>Our Needs (any that apply)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private funding institutions </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants and Subsidies • Loans • Loan guarantees • Other blended financing </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations • Incubators / Accelerators • Marketing Mentoring or Coaching • Financing Expertise • Technology Transfer Expertise • Legal / IPR advise </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member State Policy-makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To raise awareness and possibly influence policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants and Subsidies • Loans • Loan guarantees • Other blended financing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations • Incubators / Accelerators • Marketing Mentoring or Coaching • Financing Expertise • Technology Transfer Expertise • Legal / IPR advise
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party • Investor readiness training • Investor introductions • Business plan development • Expanding to more markets /finding new customers • Executive Training • Other type of Investment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Technology Organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia/Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in technical expertise • Use of research Infrastructure • Collaboration
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Angels • Venture Capital • Crowd-funding Equity • Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	We are looking for collaborations with research communities and research infrastructures engaged in developing stronger national communities of SSH scholarly communication in the European Research Area.	

About us

Other related projects	OPERAS-GER, OPERAS-PL
*Result Contributors	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología, F.S.P. (FECYT)

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	<p>CNRS—OpenEdition Max Weber Stiftung National Documentation Centre (EKT) University of Zadar CNR-ILIESI OAPEN Foundation ERIH PLUS Institute of Literary Research Polish Academy of Sciences University of Coimbra The Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU) Jisc</p>
*Owners for exploitation	
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Logo	<p>Available at: https://operas-eu.org/operas-national-nodes/</p>
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: Websites/blogs of the funded national nodes
	Link: https://operas-ger.hypotheses.org
	https://operas.pl

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	<p>National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level.</p>	
*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Please select up to three	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture and rural development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreign affairs and security policy • Fraud prevention

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Banking and financial services ● Better Regulation ● Borders and security ● Budget ● Business and industry ● Climate action ● Competition ● Consumers ● Culture and media ● Customs ● Defence ● Digital economy and society ● Economy, finance and the euro ● Education and training ● Employment and social affairs ● Energy ● Environment ● EU enlargement ● European neighbourhood policy ● Food safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Home affairs ● Humanitarian aid and civil protection ● Institutional affairs ● International Partnerships ● Justice and fundamental rights ● Maritime affairs and fisheries ● Migration and asylum ● Mobility and Transport ● Public health ● Regional policy ● Research and innovation ● Single market ● Space ● Sport ● Statistics ● Taxation ● Trade ● Transport ● Youth
*Tags / Keywords	Scholarly communication; multilingualism; bibliodiversity; open science; national communities	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal 1: No poverty ● Goal 2: Zero hunger ● Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people ● Goal 4: Quality education ● Goal 5: Gender equality ● Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation ● Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy ● Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure ● Goal 10: Reducing inequalities ● Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities ● Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production ● Goal 13: Climate action ● Goal 14: Life below water ● Goal 15: Life on land ● Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions ● Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals ● Not applicable 	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No 	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Link
	Title: D7.1 – Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes	Title: Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS National Nodes
	Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10725785	Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289238

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	Please select one
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) ● 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) ● 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) ● 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) ● 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) ● 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) ● 7 - Market Deployment ● Not applicable

*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	Currently, partners have presented a background of the work undergone by current OPERAS national nodes, an overview of the commonalities and differences between the work of the diverse nodes. They approached the challenges and opportunities presented as well, to find a common ground in which it is possible to establish common requirements for all, including issues regarding the building of the national nodes, sustainability and the positioning of OPERAS national nodes both nationally and at the European level.
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	To provide a means of coordination to the OPERAS Research Infrastructure national nodes and to support them with training materials, communication coordination and governance.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	It can be adapted to other research infrastructures and projects.
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	Our result is built to be sustained in different funding and research contexts and in many geographical locations.
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No

<p>If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?</p>	<p>Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spain France Germany Greece Croatia Finland Italy Netherlands Norway Poland Portugal Slovenia UK
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Investors Corner

<p>*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?</p>	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <100K ● 101-500K ● 501K-1M ● 1M-2.5M ● 2.6M-5M ● 5.1M-10M ● >10M ● No investment sought
<p>I can provide the following upon request by an interested party</p>	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Short presentation(s) ● Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) ● Case study(ies) ● Related Technology white paper ● A reference list of business partners, employers and/or collaborators ● List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) ● A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete and detailed business plan • Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? • Quantitative Assessment • Qualitative Assessment • Competitive Assessment • List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") • List of investors
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